

Importance of archaeological tourism

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Abstract. One of the fields of tourism is archaeological tourism. This article highlights the importance of archaeological tourism.

Key words: Archaeological tourism, UNESCO, Akhsikent, open-air museum, archaeological object, reconstruction.

Enter

Tourism network the world of the economy fast developing from the fields is one Tourism in the field to progress achieved some of countries main wealth the source is exactly the same i'm standing is considered In our country a lot fields such as i'm standing the field is also large to opportunities have in Uzbekistan i'm standing 10 ha of the area near type there is they are between visit, recreation and that's it similar one how many types developed. These between Archaeological tourism is also slow with come in is going Archeology or archaeological tourism is cultural of tourism one type, his purpose to archaeology and historical monuments storage and to them has been interest from raising consists of Archaeology and tourism between dependence ancient to history have of scientists It is probably the Renaissance to the period right will come . Archaeological tourism specialized field as cultural inheritance preserve and promote to do in the field of the matter importance pointer feature and to functions have Archaeological tourism people cultural heritage with introduces and in humans cultural to inheritance was point of view look o` changes. Archaeology tourism with binding is also state economy and culture heritage for much useful is considered

Archaeological tourism sources valuable and is unique . Because them ancient of times that's it period people by created and that's it period environment save the rest Time pass with this objects more to value have has been and this continue will continue . This is the most important thing factor archaeological to monuments harm failure to deliver, the reason each how to the memorial delivered damage again restore it won't be. That's why for tourism from sources only them another in appearance present reach through use need Such properties As for , we are archaeological sources tourism to the product to convert movement when we do , protection to do and stable to development separately attention our focus need

There are many historical monuments and holy places to be visited throughout our country. In particular, there are more than 7,300 heritage objects, of which nearly 200 are included in the UNESCO list[1].

At the same time, in order to develop archaeological tourism, our government and enthusiastic scientists have started the work of turning some monuments into "open-air museums". Uzbekistan Republic President initiative from the end of 2018 - the beginning of 2019 from Namangan region Toragorgon district Ahsikent memorial archaeological objects inside the first "Open the sky under to the museum converted". This is old city ancient Fergana of the state the capital considered in the past Characteristic that called [2]. Ahsikent ruins archaeological in terms of learning works of the 19th century the end of the 20th century from the beginning started 1885 Nicholas Veselovsky, 1914 IA Castane in the city archaeological fossil and search their work take goes _ Councils during Mikhail Masson (1939) and A. Bernshtam (1948) city on inspection their work done increases. Archaeological studies as a result of the city ark, Shahriston and from rabot consists of all three part is also separate walls with wrapped, in the arch governor palace, dungeon, in the city internal market jome mosque, Pishik from brick processed pool and ditches, in rabot artisans neighborhoods and external market there is that it was determined. Also, Ahsikent city Namangan local history museum employees also studied by (1957-1959)

Uzbekistan in 1960 Sciences Academy History and archaeology institute by organized special expedition Ahsikent 11th century from raboti to about old bathroom place determined. From the bathroom ceramic container, pipe, bucket coin and bottle items found From this except for the ruins western in the part medium for centuries about again one city ruins It was also determined that there is . Academic Yahya Gulomov and an archaeologist I. Ahrorov this studies based on this on the ground different to periods about two that it was a city, from them one ancient Ahsikent and the second Babur was born in Akhsi city that were the first to prove it. 1967 artist I. Smirnov city collected from its ruins ceramic dish, brass item and ornaments complex in Moscow East peoples state to the museum present reached Ahsikent monument of the Uzbek people culture in history important place for the state since 1950 protection obtained [3].

This from the place again defense buildings, city gates, blacksmith master and jewelers neighborhood, residences and underground water roads - water pipes _ too found [4.58] 2 directions of the aqueduct built in the form of a tunnel of brick were excavated. One of them was directed towards Shahar Arki and Shahristan neighborhoods, and the other was towards Rabat. Also, 1.5 thousand years of history

has been preserved in the cultural layer of 10-15 meters. 1.5 million-year-old cultural layers and aqueduct "turned into an open-air museum". All this increases the interest in the monument. In cooperation with Uzbekturizim, the ancient 3D view of the well-preserved places is being restored, and in the future, 10 more monuments in the Ahsikent region are planned to be closed and turned into museums for tourists.

Summary

In conclusion, it can be said that archaeological tourism is the result of interaction between tourism and archaeology. Archaeological tourism, along with the development of the country's economy, helps to restore historical events and generalize archeology. Also, this field helps to preserve the archaeological heritage, and serves to increase people's historical interest in the unknown world. Archaeological tourism the past and present time between is a bridge . His principles absolutely scientific is archaeological tourism objects huge tourism source to optimal use as strives Tourists attraction to do for heritage objects creation , reconstruction do , attention deserves places complex way present do , archeological monuments i'm standing work release rotate need This is the system through state to the economy benefit to bring with together with the history learned and new objects scientific in terms of study that's it with together, new objects digging for enough income to see can.

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